

nexus monARC project

Version 1

Description

The nexus monARC project plans to carry out research, educational, training and citizen science actions across various disciplines involving multiple layers of data collection and data types. To avoid complication in handling the various data collected during the timeline of nexus monARC is it worth identifying both the main data types expected to be collected, as well as define clear data descriptions. Both data types and descriptions can be updated during the progress of the project to provide ease of access to the data, as well as adjust particular needs identified at a later stage.

Data may be in the form of facts, observations, images, computer program results, recordings, measurements or experiences on which a research output is based.

Funder

European Commission | | EC

Grant

CAPACITY BUILDING NEXUS
FOR MONITORING WATER
QUALITY IN MULTI-STRESSOR
AREAS: PILOT STUDY AT THE
HELLENIC VOLCANIC ARC
(corda____he::101079156)

Researchers

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Organizations

National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Flemish Institute for Technological Research, University of Gothenburg, EXELISIS IKE, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Fresenius University of Applied Sciences

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [nexus monARC project](#)

Description:

The nexus monARC project plans to carry out research, educational, training and citizen science actions across various disciplines involving multiple layers of data collection and data types. To avoid complication in handling the various data collected during the timeline of nexus monARC is it worth identifying both the main data types expected to be collected, as well as define clear data descriptions. Both data types and descriptions can be updated during the progress of the project to provide ease of access to the data, as well as adjust particular needs identified at a later stage.

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [European Commission](#) | [EC](#)

Grants: CAPACITY BUILDING NEXUS FOR MONITORING WATER QUALITY IN MULTI-STRESSOR AREAS: PILOT STUDY AT THE HELLENIC VOLCANIC ARC
(corda_____he::101079156)

Project: Cite Project

3. License

License: AFL-3.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

Horizon Europe

This description provides an overall overview of the data management activities for the Horizon Europe project. It covers all types of data generated and collected during the project and describes the general principles for their handling, storage, sharing, and preservation, in line with Horizon Europe requirements and FAIR data principles.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: Dataset

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

This dataset contains raw trace element and DNA concentration data together with physicochemical measurements from seawater samples. The data were produced during scientific missions of the nexus monARC project.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

Raw data on trace element concentrations in seawater of the Hellenic Volcanic Arc were generated to support marine environmental monitoring and the future validation of citizen science data related to marine environmental quality.

Sampling was conducted during multiple field campaigns between 2023 and 2025 in the Hellenic Volcanic Arc (Aegean Sea). Sampling locations were accessed either by sailing vessel or from land. Seawater samples were collected at depths ranging from 0 to 500 m across 30 sampling stations. Geographic coordinates and sampling depths are provided for each sample.

Samples were collected using Niskin bottles or polypropylene containers, filtered through 0.20 µm cellulose filters, and preserved by acidification with suprapure nitric acid, following established trace-metal clean protocols. Samples were stored at 4 °C until analysis.

Trace element concentrations were determined using ICP-MS (Agilent 7900). Calibration was performed using internal standards. Analytical bias was assessed through the analysis of three reference materials, and analytical precision was evaluated by duplicate analyses of selected samples. The dataset contains raw analytical outputs and has not been further corrected or interpreted beyond standard instrumental processing.

The data files are provided in XLSX format and include sample identifiers, geographic coordinates, sampling depth, physicochemical in situ measurements, and elemental concentrations, reported in $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. Missing values are indicated as empty cells.

1.1.5 What is its format?

Project data were georeferenced and organized based on sampling coordinates within a GIS environment using ArcGIS Pro and stored in standard GIS file formats. The data were stored primarily in spreadsheet (XLSX) format. Supporting documentation was stored in DOCX and PDF formats, while images collected during field activities were stored in standard image formats (e.g. PNG or TIFF). During sampling activities, field records were initially documented in non-digital form (e.g. field notebooks or paper logs) and were subsequently transferred and digitized into electronic formats for data management, analysis, and long-term storage.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

0.2 MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To keep on record
- To make informed decisions
- To combine with other data

These data are released to support open science, method development, and future integration into marine environmental assessment frameworks, including those developed within the nexus monARC project. The inclusion of precise geographic coordinates enables spatial visualization and analysis of results within a GIS environment, supporting mapping-based assessments of marine environmental quality. Users are advised to consider the raw nature of the dataset and associated methodological constraints when reusing the data.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The data were generated through field sampling and measurement campaigns, laboratory analysis of sea water and sediment samples, field photographs and project events.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education
- Economy
- The public
- Industry

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

[Raw data on trace element concentrations in seawater of the Hellenic Volcanic Arc](#)

ZENODO

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18208578>

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers
- Projects identifiers

DOI

ORCID

Cordis

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

CSMD (Core Scientific Metadata Model)

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

Descriptive metadata were created for all scientific outputs, including title, authors/creators, abstract or description, keywords, and publication date, to support discovery and identification.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Metadata repository

Searchable metadata are provided through a trusted metadata repository (Zenodo), where metadata are exposed in machine-readable formats and indexed by web crawlers and search engines.

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

Biological samples

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Immediately after the end of the project, with long-term preservation and open access ensured via the Zenodo repository.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Metadata include persistent identifiers (DOIs), direct access links, access conditions, and licensing information, clearly indicating where and how the dataset/output can be accessed via the Zenodo repository.

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

Metadata will remain publicly available in the Zenodo repository even if the output itself is no longer accessible.

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Variable definitions
- Units of measurement

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

4000

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use

Direct cost

Data management costs are covered within the project budget, with the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA) responsible for data management.

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

- Use of institution infrastructure
- Infrastructure Grant

The costs will be covered through the use of institutional infrastructure and the Horizon Europe infrastructure grant, in accordance with the Grant Agreement.

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

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5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Other

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

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